

Cation Exchange Behaviour of Hydrated Ferric Oxide

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The cation exchange behaviour of hydrated ferric oxide, having reasonable chemical stability towards dilute acids, was studied. The preparative procedure, composition, chemical stability, thermogravimetric analysis, pH titrations, cation-exchange capacity and distribution coefficients (K_D) of some metal ions in resin-aqueous solution systems are reported. In addition, some binary separations of cations have also been conducted on the basis of these K_D values.

THE hydrous oxides of metals possess both the cation and anion exchange capacities at pH values above and below their isoelectric points. The proposed mechanism¹ is

According to this mechanism, the hydrated ferric oxide (isoelectric point, $\text{pH} \sim 7.1-7.2^2$) is expected to behave as an anion exchanger at low pH and as a cation exchanger at high pH region. Even though a number of studies on sorption properties of the ferric hydroxide in the form of gel, sol and crystalline types have been reported²⁻¹⁰, very little attention has so far been paid to ion exchange behaviour (cation-exchange properties, for instance), of hydrated ferric oxide. However, a few isolated investigations on adsorption of Cs^{11} , Na^{11} , K^4 and Ag^0 on ferric oxide has postulated an ion-exchange mechanism being operative. It is in this background that the present study was conducted on hydrated ferric oxide as a cation exchanger with the objective of assessing its potential in the field of analytical chemistry.

Experimental

Reagents, chemicals and instruments :

All chemicals used were of the AnalaR grade. Double distilled water was used for the preparation of solutions and their dilutions. pH measurements were conducted with Systronics expanded scale pH meter, model 331. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using the Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer, model PMQ II, 9537. A single pan balance and an electrical muffle furnace were employed for weighing and heating purposes, respectively. A glass column (internal diameter of 1.2 cm) was used for column operations.

Preparation : Ferric chloride (0.1 M) in hydrochloric acid (0.1 M) was mixed with different volumes of 1 M sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide solution. The precipitate was digested, allowed to stand with the mother liquor, filtered, thoroughly washed and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. The product was next treated with hydrochloric acid (1.0 M) and

TABLE 1—DETAILS OF SYNTHESIS AND COMPOSITION OF HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE

Batch No.	Reactants	Volume ratio (v/v)	Stirring time hr	Temp. °C	pH of mother liquor	Period of ageing hr	Colour of exchanger (H ⁺ form)	Composition Fe ₂ O ₃ : H ₂ O	Exchange capacity with respect of Na ⁺ ion/meq. g ⁻¹ at pH 12.5
B-1	0.1 M ferric chloride	1 : 10	16	80 ± 5	12.8		Black	1 : 1.28	1.28
B-1(a)	in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid + 1 M sodium hydroxide solution	1 : 10	16	27 ± 2	12.82		Reddish-black	1 : 1.3	1.32
B-2		1 : 5	16	80 ± 5	12.77		Black	1 : 1.13	1.15
B-3		1 : 2	16	„	12.65	48	Black	1 : 1.13	1.15
B-3(a)		1 : 2	4	27 ± 2	12.68		Reddish-black	1 : 1	1.05
B-4		1 : 1	16	80 ± 5	12.65		Black	1 : 1.06	1.10
B-4(a)		1 : 1	8	27 ± 2	12.65		Brown	1 : 1.05	1.10
B-5	0.1 M ferric chloride	1 : 10	16	80 ± 5	12.7		Shinning black	1 : 1.54	1.4
B-6	in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid + 1 M ammonium hydroxide solution	1 : 2	16	27 ± 2	12.6		Black with reddish tint	1 : 1.2	1.23
B-6(a)		1 : 2	8	„	12.62	48	Brown	1 : 1.18	1.17
B-7		1 : 4	8	80 ± 5	12.66		Black	1 : 1.18	1.20
B-8		1 : 1	16	„	12.6		Black	1 : 1.08	1.15

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY OF HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE IN DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS

Solvent (100 ml)	B-1		B-1(a)		B-5		B-6	
	Solubility at 100°	Solubility at 200°						
	mg							
Distilled water	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
0.1 N HCl	27.4	5.6	36.08	10.8	16.7	3.9	26.8	8.8
0.1 N HNO ₃	22.7	5.9	35.9	11.4	13.4	3.6	24.9	8.5
0.1 N H ₂ SO ₄	19.3	3.7	29.6	8.9	7.7	2.8	20.8	7.9
1 N NaOH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5% NH ₄ NO ₃ solution	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5% NH ₄ NO ₃ in 0.1 N HNO ₃	23.6	6.3	37.1	12.8	13.9	3.87	26.07	9.2
Acetone	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Acetylacetone	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

washed free of excess acid with distilled water. Finally, it was washed with a mixture of ammonium nitrate (1.0 M) and ammonium hydroxide (1.0 M) solution and then with water to remove the adhered solution. The exchanger was next heated at 105-110° to convert it from NH₄⁺ to H⁺ form and cooled over anhydrous calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. The details of synthesis and composition are recorded in Table 1. A general black appearance of these dried products (vide Column 8 of Table 1) suggests the presence of some magnetite, Fe₃O₄, along with the hydrated ferric oxides, which was later examined for their sorption behaviour. However, this is not expected to seriously affect the nature of findings in the present investigation regarding the suitability of hydrated ferric oxides as an exchanger.

Composition : About 0.5 g exchanger was taken in a silica crucible and ignited at 800° in a muffle furnace. The residue was weighed after cooling. The percent water present in the exchanger was calculated from the loss in weight, from which the ratio of Fe₂O₃ : H₂O was obtained by using the formula of Alberti *et al*¹².

Chemical stability : The exchanger was fairly stable towards low concentration (0.1 N) of acids. The solubility of the exchanger in various solvents was studied by taking 0.5 g of the sample in 100 ml of the respective solvent and shaking for 10 hr. The results are given in Table 2. The iron was estimated spectrophotometrically at 515 nm using 1,10-phenanthroline method¹³.

Heat treatment : 0.5 g exchanger was taken in a silica crucible and heated from 100 to 800° in steps of 100° for 1 hr. A separate sample was used for each run. The percent weight-loss was plotted against the temperature of heating and the curve obtained is shown in Fig. 1.

pH-Titration : Toppe and Pepper method¹⁴ was followed for the purpose by titrating 0.5 g of the exchanger pH-metrically with 100 ml portions of different solutions of MOH (and MOH+MCl) (M=Na⁺ or K⁺). The titration curves are shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b). :

Cation-exchange capacity : The cation-exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined by shak-

Fig. 1

ing 0.5 g of it with 100 ml MOH or MOH+MCl solutions of known strength at different pH (M=Na⁺, K⁺ or NH₄⁺). After equilibration, the final alkalinity was determined titrimetrically and the difference between the initial and final alkalinity gave the cation-exchange capacity of the exchanger at the given pH. The results are shown in Table 3.

The effect of time of contact on the exchange capacity of hydrated ferric oxide for Na⁺ ion is illustrated in Fig. 3. The loss in exchange capacities of hydrated ferric oxide were also determined

TABLE 3—EXCHANGE CAPACITIES WITH DIFFERENT MONOVALENT CATIONS

Medium	pH	Exchange capacity/meq. g ⁻¹	
		B-1	B-5
NaOH + NaCl	12.5	1.28	1.4
NaOH	12.5	0.96	1.12
KOH + KCl	12.5	1.44	1.62
KOH	12.5	1.12	1.25
NH ₄ OH + NH ₄ Cl	12.5	1.05	1.18
NH ₄ OH	12.5	0.87	0.99

at different temperatures at pH 12.5 by the method given above. A plot of exchange capacity vs temperature is shown in Fig. 4 for both the batches.

Distribution coefficients: The distribution coefficients (K_D values) of several cations were studied by batch measurements on the bed of the hydrated ferric oxide exchanger, heated to 200° before use. For each step, 0.5 g exchanger was equilibrated with 100 ml of the test solution ($10^{-3} M$) in different medium for 2 days with intermittent shaking. After equilibration, the metal ions were estimated complexometrically^{13,15}, and K_D values calculated by using the formula

$$K_D = \frac{\text{Initial titre value} - \text{Final titre value}}{\text{Final titre value}} \times 100$$

Wt. of exchanger taken

The results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (K_D) OF METAL IONS ON HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE (B-5) RESIN BED (HEATED AT 200°)

Metal	Water	0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃ + NH ₄ OH system (pH=12.0)	NH ₄ OH system (pH=12.0)
Pb(II)	91.2	—	—
Cu(II)	80.63	298.06	527.8
Cd(II)	51.8	177.7	397.67
Zn(II)	31.74	124.2	268.36
Mn(II)	27.4	—	—
Ni(II)	9.7	37.9	66.6
Co(II)	8.2	31.6	55.8
Ba(II)	3.8	15.2	36.16
Ca(II)	5.8	23.3	49.74
Sr(II)	4.9	20.5	48.13
Mg(II)	1.8	7.7	16.5
Hg(II)	3.6	—	—
Ce(III)	928.0	—	—
Bi(III)	837.0	—	—
Al(III)	119.0	—	—
La(III)	87.8	—	—

Fig. 2(a)

Fig. 2(b)

Fig. 3

Ion-exchange separations: Some binary separations of metal ions were conducted on the basis of their distribution coefficients on the hydrated ferric oxide column. The column was loaded with 5 g of

powdered (100-200 mesh) exchanger, heated to 200° before use, for the ion-exchange separations. Binary separations of Hg(II)-Pb(II), Hg(II)-Cu(II), Mg(II)-Pb(II), Mg(II)-Cu(II), Hg(II)-Ce(III), Mg(II)-Ce(III)

Fig. 4

TABLE 5—SEPARATIONS OF CATIONS FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION THROUGH HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE (B-5) COLUMN

Metal ions	Eluent	Amount absorbed mg	Amount recovered mg	Error %
Hg(II)	D.D.W.*	1.5033	1.49	-0.88
Pb(II)	5% NaNO ₃ + Water, pH=4.5	0.5037	0.5092	1.09
Hg(II)	D.D.W.	1.5033	1.501	-0.15
Cu(II)	5% NH ₄ NO ₃ + Water, pH=4.5	0.6322	0.6386	0.99
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	1.175	1.175	0.00
Pb(II)	5% NaNO ₃ + Water, pH=4.5	0.5037	0.5101	1.27
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	1.175	1.175	0.00
Cu(II)	5% NH ₄ NO ₃ + Water, pH=4.5	0.6322	0.6364	0.66
Hg(II)	D.D.W.	1.5033	1.5025	-0.053
Ce(III)	1 M NaNO ₃ + Water, pH=3	0.7107	0.7173	0.91
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	1.175	1.175	0.00
Ce(III)	1 M NaNO ₃ + Water, pH=3	0.7107	0.7154	0.66
Hg(II)	D.D.W.	1.5033	1.5025	-0.053
Bi(III)	1 M NaNO ₃ + Water, pH=3 [‡]	0.8214	0.8276	0.75

* D.D.W. = Double distilled water.

‡ pH of the solutions was generally adjusted with dilute nitric acid.

and Hg(II)-Bi(III) have been achieved from their aqueous mixtures, and separations of Mg(II)-Cu(II), Mg(II)-Zn(II), Ni(II)-Cu(II), Co(II)-Cu(II) and Mg(II)-Cd(II) from their ammoniacal solutions. The results are summarised in Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 6—SEPARATION OF CATIONS FROM AMMONIACAL MEDIUM THROUGH HYDRATED FERRIC OXIDE (B-5) COLUMN

Metal ions (in ammoniacal medium)	Eluent	Amount absorbed mg	Amount recovered mg	Error %
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	2.175	2.164	-0.50
Cu(II)	1 M NaNO ₃ + 0.01 N HNO ₃	0.943	0.945	0.21
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	2.175	2.170	-0.23
Zn(II)	1 M NaNO ₃ + 0.001 N HNO ₃	0.993	0.995	0.20
Ni(II)	5% NH ₄ NO ₃ solution, (pH 6)	1.946	1.938	-0.41
Cu(II)	1 M NaNO ₃ + 0.01 N HNO ₃	0.943	0.946	0.34
Co(II)	5% NH ₄ NO ₃ solution (pH 6)	2.238	2.229	-0.40
Cu(II)	1 M NaNO ₃ + 0.01 N HNO ₃	0.943	0.944	0.11
Mg(II)	D.D.W.	2.175	2.175	0.00
Cd(II)	1 M NaNO ₃ + 0.01 N HNO ₃	0.937	0.986	-0.11

Results and Discussion

It is seen from Table 1 that B-1 and B-5 are suitable for use as cation exchangers. Besides possessing high exchange capacities, they have the added advantage of being fairly inert towards dilute acids. B-1 is more stable than B-1(a) while B-5 is the most stable in the series. The solubility of the exchanger decreases with an increase in temperature, being low at 200°. Thus, any difficulty arising of its likely dissolution at the time of ion-exchange separation could be minimised by maintaining the exchanger at 200°. Furthermore, organic solvents do not affect the solubility of the hydrated ferric oxide exchanger.

As for exchange properties, the exchangers (B-1 and B-5) were characterised as being monofunctional by the pH-titration curves, and the cation-exchange capacities were found to be different for various cations. For monovalent cations, for example, the sequence $K^+ > Na^+ > NH_4^+$ was followed for the cation-exchange capacities on the given exchanger, the order being the same for both the batches (B-1 and B-5). Fig. 3 reveals that the time of contact does affect the exchange capacity and an equilibrium exchange was attained in nearly 18 hr with both the batches. A knowledge of the time for equilibration is necessary to ensure minimum error in the determination of exchange capacity and distribution coefficients of metal ions. Fig. 4 shows that the exchange capacity of hydrated ferric oxide decreases with increase of temperature. However, some residual exchange capacity of the exchangers was indicated even at a temperature as high as 800° (vide Fig. 4).

In view of the rather low acid-solubility of the hydrated ferric oxide, it can be successfully used as an ion-exchanger in column separation operations. For this purpose, a knowledge of the distribution coefficient (K_D) of the appropriate metal ions on the bed of the exchanger is necessary. The K_D values were determined by subjecting the bed to heating at 200° prior to use, which reduces the sorption on the surface by way of squeezing. The K_D values for various metal ions are in the order Ce(III) > Bi(III) > Al(III) > La(III), Pb(II) > Cu(II) > Cd(II) > Zn(II) > Mn(II) > Ni(II), Co(II) > Ca(II), Sr(II) > Ba(II), Hg(II) > Mg(II).

The tripositive ions were more favourably exchanged by the hydrated ferric oxide phase than the bivalent ones, evidently an example of ionic potential effect.

The use of hydrated ferric oxide also rendered possible some binary separations of cations from aqueous solutions with reproducibilities within about $\pm 1.5\%$. However, separation of metal ions from ammoniacal solutions provides a better promise. In this medium, the metal ions tend to form ammine-complexes and can easily be eluted out by using a suitable eluting agent. The reproducibility of such separations was about $\pm 0.5\%$. It is evident from the results recorded in Tables 5 and 6 that the hydrated ferric oxide can be put to use for (even) quantitative separation of several toxic (heavy metal) cations from aqueous mixtures.

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